

A Comparative Study between Sodium Arsenate and Sodium Arsenite Induced Histopathological Changes in Mice

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Among the various environmental toxicants affecting human health, heavy metal toxicity has gained increasing significance in recent years, with arsenic toxicity emerging as a major concern. Among the different compounds of arsenic containing compounds, arsenite and arsenate are primary contributors to water contamination. This paper compares the histopathological changes induced by sodium arsenate and arsenite in BALB/c mice.

Materials and methods: Mice were categorized into five distinct groups - group 1-5. Group 1 functioned as the untreated control, whereas Groups 2 and 3 were administered sodium arsenate at respective doses of 6 mg/kg and 12 mg/kg of body weight. Meanwhile, groups 4 and 5 received sodium arsenite at doses of 10 mg/kg and 15 mg/kg body weight, respectively, over a period of 28 days.

Result: No statistically significant changes were detected in the histopathological alterations in various organs of both the sodium arsenate-treated groups. However, the sodium arsenite-treated groups exhibited notable degenerative changes in the brain, damage to renal tubules, stomach erosion, and depletion of germ cells in the testis.

Conclusion: On the basis of above observations, it can be concluded that between the two forms of arsenic, compared to sodium arsenate, sodium arsenite is more toxic than sodium arsenate, leading to more pronounced histopathological alterations in various organs.

Key Words: Arsenic, Sodium Arsenate, Sodium Arsenite, Toxicant.

INTRODUCTION:

The environment possesses several heavy metals in their Earth's crust which evolve either through natural sources like volcanic eruption, release from the soil etc or through human activities of industrial processes, metal refining, combustion of coal in power plants, combustion of petroleum fuels, timber preservation, Nuclear power plant operations, high-voltage transmission lines plastic and textile manufacturing etc. Arsenic is one such heavy metal whose tremendous increase in the environment has created serious health concerns throughout the world. Drinking water is a major source of arsenic contamination, where it is noticed in trivalent (arsenite, As III), and pentavalent (arsenate, As V) forms. In the majority of studied species, it is reported that arsenite exhibits greater toxicity than arsenate, although significant variations have been observed.^[1] Arsenite, which is highly toxic is a prevalent inorganic arsenic compound.^[2] The toxicity of Sodium arsenite (As III) is reported to be about 60 times greater than sodium arsenate (As V).^[3] Exposure to arsenite induces oxidative stress, triggering cellular responses that contribute to arsenic-related toxicity and carcinogenicity. Arsenic

exposure can result in skin disorders including hyperkeratosis and pigmentation changes, nerve tissue damage, chronic lung disease, reproductive complications, and a heightened risk of developing cancers of the skin, liver, lungs, kidneys, and urinary bladder.^[4] Short-term exposure to inorganic arsenic can cause failure in multiple organs and may result in death. Prolonged exposure is linked to immune system toxicity, the development of various cancers, and impaired function in several organs such as the liver, kidneys, nervous system, and cardiovascular system.^[5] Additionally, non-cancer health effects resulting from arsenic exposure include skin keratosis, diabetes, heart-related conditions, and disorders of skin pigmentation. The kidney, a key organ for arsenic elimination from the body, is highly vulnerable to its harmful effects.^[6] Arsenic metabolized in liver through methylation, generating organ arsenicals that are excreted in urine. Prolonged exposure to arsenic causes renal (kidney) damage by triggering elevated generation of free radicals within the nephrons.^[7]

As per WHO recommendations the maximum permissible concentration of arsenic in drinking water is 10µg/L.^[8] In recent years, concerns have

grown regarding environmental metal contamination and its bioaccumulation within food chains.^[9] In India, an estimated 6 million individuals are impacted by arsenic toxicity. High concentrations (>50 ppb) of arsenic are noticed in water being consumed by people living in West Bengal and Bangladesh^[10]. In order to reach out to a proper remediation therapy for arsenic induced toxicity, there is a necessity to understand the actual form of arsenic which is more harmful. The researcher in this study, aims to examine the histopathological changes in mice by administering different doses of both forms of Arsenic i.e. sodium arsenate and sodium arsenite.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Sodium Arsenate and sodium arsenite was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Dushivishari and honey prepared by a GMP certified pharmacy was purchased from local market.

Animals and housing conditions:

Animals:

In all, A total of 30 adult male BALB/c mice, which weighed about 25 and 30 grams, were obtained from the Department of Zoology, Institute of Science BHU. The animals were kept in polypropylene cages and maintained under standard environmental conditions, at a temperature of $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and a 12-hour light/dark cycle, and where freely accessible to a standard diet and drinking water. Prior to the experiment, they were acclimated to laboratory conditions for 14 days. All experimental procedures were designed in accordance of the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of the Institute under the assigned approval number (BHU/DoZ/IAEC/2022-2023/015).

Experimental design:

All animals were randomly divided to five groups, with six animals in each group (n=6).

Group 1 (Normal control) : Mice received normal saline (The same volume as other groups)

Group 2 :The mice received sodium arsenate at a dose of 6 mg per kilogram body weight.

Group 3: Mice received sodium Arsenate at 12 mg per kilogram body weight

Group 4: Mice received sodium arsenite at dose 10mg per kilogram body weight

Group 5: Mice received sodium arsenite at dose 15 mg per kilogram body weight.

All groups (except group 1) received sodium arsenate and Sodium arsenite, dissolved in distilled water, administered once daily for a period of 28 days through oral gavage (20 no.).

RESULTS:

Histopathological study:

After 28 days, the mice were sacrificed for histopathological assessment. The brain, stomach, liver, kidneys, testes, and heart were collected, fixed in a 10% (w/v) formalin solution, and sent for histopathological examination.

Histopathological changes:

Brain:

The brain tissue sections include the cerebrum, cerebellum, and hippocampus.

In group 1 (normal control) most of the neurons in the cerebrum and hippocampus appeared healthy, marked by a pale, rounded nucleus, well-defined nuclear borders, and prominent nucleoli. In group 2 & 3 section of brain (sodium arsenate – 6 and 12 mg/kg bw) cerebral cortex showed normal neurons with round to oval nuclei and abundant cytoplasm. Occasional cells showed shrunken, hyperchromatic nuclei. In group 4 (sodium arsenite- 10mg/kg bw) - Certain neurons in the cerebrum, along with those in the CA1 and CA3 regions of the hippocampus, exhibited degeneration, appearing shrunken with dark basophilic nuclei. Additionally, sections of one mice exhibited focal areas of chronic lymphocytic infiltration in the cerebrum. However, the overall tissue architecture remained unchanged. In group 5 (sodium arsenite- 15mg/kg bw), degenerated neurons were observed in the CA1 region of the hippocampus and cerebrum in both slides. There was no evidence of inflammatory infiltration or necrotic neurons. The overall tissue architecture remained intact.

Figure 1:

(A)- Normal control group showing healthy neurons (B)- Sodium Arsenate(dose6mg/kgbw) showing normal neurons (C)- Sodium Arsenate (dose 12mg/kgbw) showing normal neurons (D)- Sodium arsinite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) showing degenerating neurons (E) Sodium arsenite (dose 15 mg/kgbw) showing degenerating neurons.

Stomach

In group 1, no significant histological changes were observed. The tissue architecture remained intact, with no signs of inflammation or necrosis. In group 2 & 3 stomach showed mucosal lining with diffuse hyperplasia of epithelial cells. Muscularis and sub-muscularis were normal. While in group 4, compared to group 1(control), the mucosa appeared atrophic, showing a reduction in both its layers and glandular structures. Mild epithelial erosion was present, with

no signs of inflammatory infiltration. In group 5, the mucosa appeared atrophic, characterized by a reduction in both its layers and glandular structures. Mild epithelial erosion was observed in the mucosa. In the slide, the non-glandular region of the stomach exhibits an abscess with neutrophilic debris extending into the epithelial layers. Additionally, severe acute and chronic inflammatory infiltration was present across all three layers of the non-glandular region of the stomach in the slide.

Figure 2:

(A)Normal control group showing no histological change (B)- Sodium Arsenate(dose6mg/kgbw) showing normal muscularis(C)- Sodium Arsenate (dose 12mg/kgbw) showing normal muscularis (D)- Sodium arsinite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) (D)- Sodium arsinite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) showing mild erosion is seen in the epithelium of the mucosa. (E) Sodium arsenite (dose 15 mg/kgbw) showing acute and chronic inflammatory infiltrate in mucosa.

Liver:

In group 1, The slide showed no histological changes, such as degeneration, inflammation, or necrosis. The tissue architecture remained intact. In groups 2 and 3, the liver exhibited normal hepatic architecture with well-preserved central hepatic cords, whereas in group 4, compared to the group 1 (control), no histological changes such as degeneration,

inflammation, or necrosis were observed in the slides. The tissue architecture remained unchanged. In group 5, focal areas of early necrosis were observed, characterized by the loss of cytoplasmic and nuclear details, along with acute inflammatory infiltration. Additionally, diffuse cytoplasmic vacuolation of hepatocytes was present.

Figure 3:

(A) Normal control group showing no histological change (B)- Sodium Arsenate(dose 6mg/kgbw) showing normal hepatic architecture (C)- Sodium Arsenate (dose 12mg/kgbw) showing normal hepatic architecture (D)- Sodium arsenite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) showing no change in tissue architecture. (E) Sodium arsenite (dose 15 mg/kgbw) showing focal necrosis with acute inflammatory infiltration.

Kidneys:

In group 1, no histological changes, such as degeneration, inflammation, or necrosis, were observed in the slide. The tissue architecture remained unchanged. In group 2&3 all glomeruli showed normal glomerular thickening lined by single endothelial cells and few tubules showed mild tubular necrosis. While in group 4, slide showed dilated and

degenerated tubules, with cells exhibiting pale cytoplasm and sloughing remnants in the lumen. The tissue architecture remained unchanged. In group 5, dilated and degenerated tubules were observed in both the cortex and medulla of the slides. Some tubules in the medulla contained renal casts. The tissue architecture remained unchanged.

Figure 4:

(A) Normal control group showing no histological change (B)- Sodium Arsenate(dose 6mg/kgbw) showing normal tubules (C)- Sodium Arsenate (dose 12mg/kgbw) showing normal tubules (D)- Sodium arsenite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) showing dilated and degenerated tubules. (E) Sodium arsenite (dose 15 mg/kgbw) showing dilated and degenerated tubules.

Testes:

Group 1,2 & 3 showed no histological changes like necrosis of tubules. Group 4 showed reduced size of tubules and reduction in number of tubules. Degenerated tubules with depletion and degenerated germ cells were seen. In group 5, Most of the tubules

exhibited degeneration, characterized by a marked depletion of germ cells, disorganization of germ cells, Germ cells were found exfoliated into the lumen of the seminiferous tubules. Tubular necrosis was also seen.

Figure 5:

(A) Normal control group showing no histological change (B)- Sodium Arsenate(dose6mg/kgbw) showing no histological change (C)- Sodium Arsenate (dose 12mg/kgbw) showing no histological change (D)- Sodium arsenite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) showing degenerated tubules with depletion of germ cells. (E) Sodium arsenite (dose 15 mg/kgbw) showing degenerated tubules with depletion of germ cells.

Heart:

In group 1,2&3 histological changes like degeneration, inflammation and necrosis were not seen in the slide. No change was noticed in the tissue architecture. Most of the cardiac myocytes appeared normal with central oval nuclei. In group 4, few discrete, clear vacuoles were seen in the cytoplasm of the cardiomyocytes in some areas. Histological

changes like inflammation and necrosis were not seen in the slide. No change in tissue architecture. In group 5, discrete, clear vacuoles were seen in the cytoplasm of the cardiomyocytes in many areas. Compared with Group 4, more vacuoles were seen. Histological changes like inflammation and necrosis were not seen in the slide. No change was seen in the tissue architecture.

Figure 6:

(A) Histological changes like degeneration, inflammation and necrosis is not seen in the slide. No change in tissue architecture (B)- Sodium Arsenate(dose6mg/kgbw) showing no histological change, necrosis and no change in tissue architecture. (C)- Sodium Arsenate (dose 12mg/kgbw) showing no histological

change and tissue architecture (D)- Sodium arsinite (dose 10 mg/kgbw) showing Few discrete, clear vacuoles are seen in the cytoplasm of the cardiomyocytes in some areas. (E) Sodium arsenite (dose 15 mg/kgbw) showing Discrete, clear more vacuoles are seen in the cytoplasm of the cardiomyocytes in many areas.

DISCUSSION:

The main interest of this work was to compare the histopathological changes in the organs of mice following repeated administration of fixed doses of sodium arsenate and arsenite. The doses used in this investigation were determined based on the histopathological effects observed with these two different inorganic arsenic forms. While previous studies have indicated that sodium arsenate may exhibit toxic properties, our findings suggest that small doses of sodium arsenate (6 and 12 mg/kg body weight) resulted in minimal toxicity, showing no significant impact on the tissue structure of the viscera. In this study, we performed histopathological analyses on multiple organs, including the liver, kidneys, brain, heart, and lungs spleen, jejunum, stomach, and testes, for both groups. At the administered doses of 6 and 12 mg/kg body weight, sodium arsenate did not induce any significant histopathological alterations in these organs when compared to the normal control group, taken orally with drinking water over a 28-day period. In contrast, administration of sodium arsenite at 10 and 15 mg/kg body weight exhibited signs of toxicity in six critical organs: the brain, stomach, liver, kidney, testes, and heart. The spleen, jejunum, and lungs, however, showed no histopathological alterations relative to the normal control group.

Among the groups of mice administered sodium arsenite at both dose levels, neurons in the cerebrum and hippocampus exhibited degeneration, characterized by shrunken cell bodies and dark basophilic nuclei. Research has demonstrated that chronic arsenic exposure leads to oxidative stress and inflammation in brain tissue^[11], which may have contributed to these observed changes. Furthermore, it has been proven that trivalent arsenic can generate reactive oxygen species, responsible for apoptosis in neuronal cells^[12] thereby increasing the risk of neurodegeneration^{[13] - [15]}

Regarding the histopathological changes observed in the stomach, the group which was fed with sodium arsenite showed marked alterations compared to the control group. The mucosa appeared atrophic, with a reduction in both its layers and glandular structures. Mild epithelial erosion was present, accompanied by no signs of inflammatory infiltration. With the higher dose of 15 mg/kg body weight, the mucosa continued to show atrophy and a reduction in its layers and glandular structures. Additionally, the slides revealed an abscess in the non-glandular region of the stomach, containing neutrophilic debris that extended into the epithelial layers. Severe acute and

chronic inflammatory infiltration was noted across all three layers of the non-glandular region. These findings indicate that when arsenic contamination originates from drinking water, the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) becomes a target organ, leading to expected structural changes in the gastric mucosa. Research supports the notion that arsenic exposure may trigger oxidative stress and enhance mRNA gene expression associated with inflammation in the stomach of birds^[16]. Furthermore, significant increases in H₂O₂ and malondialdehyde (MDA), decrease in total superoxide dismutase (T-SOD) activity and glutathione (GSH) levels has also been observed in the mucosa of gastric lining of arsenic exposed mice. This disturbance of the oxidant-antioxidant balance in the gastric tissue contributes to the inflammatory responses.^[17]

In the sodium arsenite 15mg/kg BW treated group, focal areas of early necrosis were observed in the histopathology of liver tissues characterized by the loss of cytoplasmic and nuclear details, along with acute inflammatory infiltration. Additionally, diffuse cytoplasmic vacuolation of hepatocytes was present. Previous studies have demonstrated that arsenic exposure triggers oxidative stress, disrupts liver metabolism, induces ferroptosis (characterized by lipid peroxidation), and compromises the intestinal barrier of hepatocytes.^{[18].- [20]} Additionally, arsenic can disrupt the balance of antioxidants, promote oxidative stress, causes increase in the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and accelerates lipid peroxidation ^{[21]- [22]}. Furthermore, oxidative stress has potential to initiate inflammation, which is characterized by the infiltration of inflammatory cells and the release of mediators. These changes may also account for the alterations observed in hepatocytes in this study.

There was normal tissue architecture in the kidneys with no changes observed in the sodium arsenate fed mice. While in the mice fed with 10mg/kg body weight sodium arsenite, slides of kidney showed dilated and degenerated tubules, with cells exhibiting pale cytoplasm and sloughing remnants in the lumen. The tissue architecture remained unchanged. In group fed with 15mg/kg body weight sodium arsenite, dilated and degenerated tubules were observed in both the cortex and medulla of the slides. Some tubules in the medulla contained renal casts. Anyhow, the tissue architecture remained unchanged.

The primary organ responsible for the excretion of arsenic is the kidney, making the observed damage to the renal tubules anticipated, as supported by

previous studies.^{[23],[24]} Enhanced transcription factor DNA binding and gene expression induced by arsenite or arsenate in renal slices.^[25] Additionally, research indicates that sub chronic exposure to arsenic alter the expression of inflammatory cytokines and initiate inflammatory response in both the liver and kidneys. Enhanced renal myeloperoxidase (MPO) activity may also contribute to renal tissue damage and inflammation. ^[26] Also research suggest that the kidney, being rich in phospholipids, undergoes oxidative degradation of these lipids with chronic arsenic exposure. Thus, it can be proposed that arsenic-induced lipid peroxidation plays a significant role in contributing to in the kidney causes to oxidative damage which may further lead to impairment in kidney functions.^[27]

With regards to the testis, the sodium arsenite group fed in the dose of 10mg/kg BW showed reduced size of tubules and reduction in number of tubules. Degenerated tubules with depletion and degenerated germ cells were evident. In the 15mg/kg BW group, most of the tubules were degenerated characterised by depletion of germ cells, disorganization of germ cells, exfoliation.

Research has already established that arsenic induces testicular toxicity, with arsenic-exposed mice exhibiting gradual reductions in seminiferous tubular diameter and various gametogenic cell populations.^{[28],[29]} Also, cell death or apoptosis is induced by arsenic in the testicular germ cells. ^[30] ^[31] Furthermore, arsenic exposure can induce cell death or apoptosis in testicular germ cells and promote reactive oxygen species (ROS)-related cytotoxicity and apoptotic cell death in mouse TM4 Sertoli cells.^[32] Thus, arsenic toxicity may result in direct damages to testicular component cells leading to spermatogenic dysfunction.

The doses of sodium arsenite and sodium arsenate were determined based on previous studies ^{[33],[34]} selecting the closest possible approximations for both groups. Despite these prior studies, we did not observe any histopathological changes in the 11 organs examined at the selected dose of sodium arsenate. However, sodium arsenite demonstrated significant histopathological changes in 6 of the 11 organs studied at the specified dose.

CONCLUSION:

Histopathological examination is regarded as the “gold standard” for assessing organ damage and serves as definitive evidence of toxicity from a particular chemical dose. In this study, regarding the two inorganic arsenic compounds, sodium arsenate at doses of 6 mg/kg body weight and 12 mg/kg body weight failed to demonstrate any histopathological damage and showed results similar to the control group. In contrast, sodium arsenite at doses of 10 mg/kg body weight and especially at 15 mg/kg body

weight exhibited significant multi-organ toxicity. These findings emphasize the importance of understanding the specific mechanisms of action associated with different arsenic species, as this knowledge is crucial for risk assessment and management of arsenic exposure in both humans and animals. Further investigations are needed to clarify the exact pathways through which arsenite induces organ damage and to explore potential protective strategies against its toxic effects. Additionally, these results highlight the necessity of carefully considering different forms of arsenic in environmental health research and regulatory policies aimed at minimizing exposure to highly toxic species such as arsenite, especially in sources of drinking water.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

There are no conflicts of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS:

As III: Sodium arsenite, As V: Sodium Arsenate, WHO: World Health Organisation, GMP: Good Manufacturing Practices, CA: Cornu ammonis, GIT: Gastrointestinal tract, mRNA: Messenger ribonucleic acid, MDA: malondialdehyde, T-SOD: Total Superoxide Dismutase GSH: Glutathione, ROS: reactive oxygen species, DNA: Deoxyribonucleic acid MPO: myeloperoxidase

Ethical Statements: Approved by the institutional ethical committee assigned approval number (BHU/DoZ/IAEC/2022-2023/ 015).

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